

STAGES OF ORGANIZING PEDAGOGICAL RHETORIC WITH STUDENTS

Pakhratdinov Sultan Yunisovich

Researcher, Tashkent State Pedagogical University

Аннотация: Ўқитувчининг риторик маданияти, маънавий оламининг кенглиги муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Ўқитувчиларнинг педагогик риторикани ташкил этиш босқичларида педагогик риторика маданиятни мунтазам шакллантириб бориши, ўқитувчининг педагогик риторика этикаси ва одоб-ахлоқи, дилкашлиги, муошарат одобига алоҳида талаблари ўз аксини топган. Ўқитувчининг талабалар билан бўлажак риторикани моделлаштиришнинг муҳим шарти ўқитувчи ва талабаларнинг ўзаро эмоционал бирлигини таъминлаши ушбу мақолада ёритилган.

Kalit sózlar: Риторика, Коммуникатив, компетенция, импровизация, аудитория, моделлаштириш, атмосфера, метод.

Аннотация: Важна риторическая культура учителя, широта его духовного мира. На этапах организации педагогической риторики педагогов закономерно формируется педагогическая риторическая культура, находят отражение особые требования педагога к педагогической риторической этике и манерам, сердечности, коммуникативному этикету. Важным условием моделирования учителем будущей риторики с учащимися является обеспечение взаимного эмоционального единства между учителем и учащимися.

Ключевые слова: Риторика, Коммуникативность, компетентность, импровизация, аудитория, моделирование, атмосфера, метод.

Annotation: The teacher's rhetorical culture and the breadth of his spiritual world are important. In the stages of organizing the pedagogical rhetoric of the teachers, the pedagogical rhetorical culture is regularly formed, the teacher's special requirements for the pedagogical rhetorical ethics and manners, cordiality, communication etiquette are

reflected. An important condition for the teacher's modeling of the future rhetoric with students is the provision of mutual emotional unity between the teacher and students.

Key words: Rhetoric, Communication, competence, improvement, audience, modeling, atmosphere, method.

Taking into account the specific features of the content of preparation for teaching rhetoric, the teacher's professional ability to teach rhetoric, his wishes and opportunities to successfully teach rhetoric to students with appropriate professional training are taken into account. It should be noted that the teacher's rhetoric with students during the educational process has an important educational value. This requires increasing its spiritual content in the entire system of pedagogical rhetoric, because pedagogical rhetoric is aimed at forming the moral foundations of education. The complex unity of socio-psychological, educational and spiritual tasks places high demands on the teacher's communicative activity. Based on many years of theoretical and practical experience, we would like to emphasize that the teacher's pedagogical rhetoric can be implemented through the following stages:

1. Prognostic stage: Modeling any type of future rhetoric with the audience, students in the process of direct preparation for rhetoric by the teacher.

2. Early period of rhetoric: Taking the initiative in the process of organizing the initial rhetoric with students in the audience, directly using the methods of interaction.

3. Effective use and management of various forms of rhetoric in improving and developing pedagogical activity.

4. Modeling the rhetorical system to be carried out for further pedagogical activity and continuously analyzing the implemented system of rhetoric.

At the first stage of rhetoric, modeling, it is necessary to prepare to meet with students, to think not only about the content of the upcoming activity, but also about the possible methods and effective tones of rhetoric. It is necessary to think carefully in advance, imagining how important this initial stage of pedagogical rhetoric is. It

provides an opportunity to plan the communicative system of any training in a perfect, unique way.

At this prognostic stage, a complex process of transferring pedagogical tasks to the field of communicative tasks is carried out. Their compatibility is achieved. At the same time, the perception of the students, the new learning material being learned by the audience and the personality of the teacher are observed and evaluated.

The teacher can try to make his own communicative plan for the upcoming lesson. Certain methods of communicative tasks are suitable for each pedagogical task of training, and specific directions of its solution are shown in it.

An important condition for modeling the future rhetoric with students is the mutual emotional unity of the teacher and students, which gives the teacher the opportunity to foresee the following possible atmosphere of the lesson:

- to be able to anticipate various situations that may occur with the student team in the upcoming training;

- organization of various levels of democratic and free interaction with students, defining prospects for its development; машфулотда талабаларнинг билишга бўлган қизиқишини ва ижодий кайфиятини вужудга келтириш.

The analysis of the work experience of advanced teachers shows that it is very important to model the future rhetoric with students during the training, because this process comprehensively determines the didactic principles of the training, directs the teacher to creative activity, in which there is an opportunity to improve various models of rhetoric in relation to the perfect forms of interaction with students. Rhetoric modeling can be done quickly right before a new activity, and sometimes it takes on a permanent character. It creates an opportunity for the teacher to anticipate his communicative attitude and emotional behavior and feelings during the training process.

In the second stage of rhetoric - in organizing a direct relationship with the audience group, the teacher should take the initiative and communicative advantage, which will give him the opportunity to manage the continuous rhetoric in the next stages. Initiative in rhetoric ensures that the teacher always manages the educational

process wisely. As long as the teacher does not always have the opportunity to direct the rhetoric with the student body.

In the second stage, the conditions and system of the future rhetoric will be defined, and the pre-planned model of rhetoric will be implemented. In the first moments of the rhetoric, the teacher should clarify the possibilities of using the selected educational methods, feel the general mood of the students, their creativity and working mood.

Modern socio-psychological research shows that a person can be an initiator in rhetoric, and sometimes, depending on the situation, can participate as an active or passive subject of interaction. A characteristic feature of professional-pedagogical rhetoric is that the teacher's initiative in this place also controls the entire educational process as a means of managing rhetoric. It should be said that from the socio-psychological point of view, the management of the research aimed at gaining knowledge in the mutual creative activities of the teacher and the students during the training is carried out only as a result of properly organized rhetoric.

For example, it is necessary for the teacher to inculcate a new topic in the minds of students, to organize rhetoric with the class team when explaining new material or to create a problem situation, as a result of which the students become a cohesive team, they think and search for each other during the training and learning. The teacher's initiative in rhetoric provides an opportunity to find a solution to a number of strategic and tactical problems from an educational and socio-psychological point of view: the guiding role of the teacher in the educational process, the necessary socio-psychological environment that forms the good mood and emotions of students and ensures the effectiveness of educational activities. It is provided to direct the intense positive rhetoric that gives the opportunity to create, in accordance with the pedagogical purpose.

The initiative of the teacher in organizing rhetoric with the student team is manifested in the following situations:

- reasonable and careful organization of the initial interview process with the students;

- quick transition from organizational ceremonies and events (greetings, conducting students in an orderly manner, etc.) to official and personal rhetoric;
- easy to achieve socio-psychological cooperation with the students;
- not to allow any negative obstacles to appear in the organization and content of interaction with students;
- to show his personal human qualities in interaction with students;
- elimination of negative attitudes towards certain students;
- to organize a holistic interaction with all the students;
- conscious setting of tasks and issues that can mobilize the student community to free rhetoric in the initial situations of mutual cooperation;
- not to apply the prohibited pedagogical requirements in the education and training system, on the contrary, to increase new, tested, technologically perfect pedagogical requirements;
- ensuring the external communicative appearance of the teacher (moderateness, orderliness, activity, politeness, social etiquette, etc.);
- using verbal and non-verbal means of interaction, actively engaging in a relationship through mimicry, pantomime, and a meaningful look;
- "showing" one's goodwill, inclination, friendship to the student community;
- to be able to set bright and attention-grabbing goals of pedagogical activity with students and show ways to achieve them;
- to be able to understand, take into account and show solidarity with students' inner moods and feelings in various situations.

In pedagogic training and manuals, education is interpreted as a collaborative activity of teachers and students, a means of mutual positive influence on each other. However, the socio-psychological system of this activity is not always taken into account. Here too, a number of problems arise that can negatively affect the content and methodical aspects of education. Mutual cooperation envisages the socio-psychological unity of the teacher and students. This is often lacking in training.

According to research conducted by pedagogic scientists, there are 25 to 150 cases of psychological mismatch between teachers and students during training. These are not consciously controlled, which means that a specific goal is not set by the teacher. On the contrary, a rhetorical system that is correctly found and used in training activates students, creates a desire for interested participation in educational activities. Thus, the socio-psychological aspect of educational activity is considered a practical resource for optimizing education. Sometimes it is necessary to look not for new methods of education, but for reliable socio-psychological support of existing methods.

The analysis of the psychological characteristics of withdrawals in the behavior of students who do not learn from classes shows that his negative feelings, passivity in the relationship with his peers, changeable behavior appear as a result of his dissatisfaction not only with his work, but also with his position in the student body and the rhetoric that lacks friendly relations with him. All these situations lead to a sharp change in the student's psychological mood.

In the system of pedagogical rhetoric of teachers, the perception and thinking of one or another student are often formed in one mold, and in the eyes of the teacher, they become objects of stable psychological rhetoric. Therefore, if the student becomes "bad-behaved" in the eyes of the teacher, this affects the teacher's rhetorical practice towards him. A.A. Leontev notes the following signs of such an attitude: during training, the teacher devotes less time to a "bad" student to answer a question related to the topic than to a "good" student, that is, he does not draw his attention to him, does not give him time to think. If the student answers incorrectly, the teacher does not return the question, directs the question, or immediately asks another student without giving feedback, or gives the correct answer himself. Sometimes, he can use the "liberal style" by evaluating the wrong answer positively. Meanwhile, the "bad" student is punished for the wrong answer. No praise for correct answers. The reaction of the teacher to any answer of the "bad" student is not noticeable, he calls another student to answer, sometimes even with "bad" students he does not conduct a completely effective pedagogical rhetoric.

At the third stage of rhetoric, the teacher effectively uses various forms of pedagogical communication and performs the following multifunctional tasks:

- during the training, the teacher solves many pedagogical methods and tools, as well as personal communicative competences;
- in fact, in different parts of the training process, the teacher is required to use specific systems of rhetoric in educational influence;
- an experienced teacher will find these systems almost easily, it may be difficult for teachers who have just started their teaching career.

Pedagogically correct organization of rhetoric in the teacher's professional activity requires serious demands on his communicative culture. Training and educational activities are the process that forms the system of teacher-student interaction, and it is in this activity that the teacher forms his personal pedagogical activity. From mutual conversations with experienced teachers, it is known that in order to choose the form of rhetoric with a group of students, the teacher in some sense is required to choose pedagogical methods for the new material being studied. Therefore, it is necessary to model the rich aspects of the rhetorical system when preparing to learn a new topic in training and when creating a plan of educational impact.

A young teacher, who is just beginning his pedagogical career, must know that in the process of interaction with students, especially in his professional pedagogical behavior, he will face specific psychological obstacles, that conflicts may arise in rhetoric with students, and he should prepare for this in every way, and have deep pedagogical and psychological knowledge.

A young teacher may not have rhetorical skills, which causes negative situations such as stuttering and confusion, inability to move freely. These teachers may have a lack of advanced expressive means of rhetoric, do not know how to use speech techniques, and inaccuracy in mime and pantomimic actions. Sometimes, as a result of the use of "authoritarian style" of rhetoric during the educational process, the teacher and the class team have negative consequences. Pedagogical activities in which educational tasks, various tasks and educational activities are carried out in

general due to the deep knowledge and skills of a young teacher may not be interesting for students, or they may be completely indifferent. Any pedagogical activities that the teacher thinks are interesting may not affect the students. Sometimes, as a result of the same pattern of negative rhetoric with the student body, the teacher does not "get along" with them, and as a result, he is forced to leave the student body. The new teacher learns the secrets of the mood of protest that happened in rhetoric with the previous teacher of the class team, tries to apply his own rhetorical position. However, it should not be forgotten that the mood of protest in the relationship of the student community with the teacher may also affect the teacher, who may not be able to remove the negative mood of the community towards him in rhetoric.

In the fourth stage of rhetoric, the rhetorical system for pedagogical activity is modeled and the realized system of rhetoric is analyzed. Pedagogical rhetoric from a teacher:

- quick and accurate psychological analysis in any changing conditions of interaction in the class team;

- well-planned implementation of the communicative system, and especially its most important branch - speech technique and the influence of public speaking;

- quickly and accurately find the "communicative competences" corresponding to the individual professional creativity of the teacher and the ability to communicate with students in different situations, as well as the personal characteristics of the student;

- at the same time, feeling that there is also an inverse relationship of rhetoric, demanding its modeling and support.

The teacher sometimes faces communicative problems that need to be solved quickly and precisely in the emergency situations that arise in his daily work, and he feels that he is not ready for unexpected situations of rhetoric. In such situations, the teacher's intelligence and pedagogical culture, professional thinking, the development of speech and the presence of lexical and professional-lexical vocabulary, general conversational culture, tendency to communicative activity with students play the

main role. Taking advantage of unexpected, unprepared communicative problems is a huge test in the teacher's professional activity and is of principle importance, because in such situations it is impossible to roughly plan all options of rhetoric. In this, the teacher must have the ability to develop skills in situations of pedagogical improvisation (without preparation) in rhetoric - quickly and truthfully assess the situation and students' behavior with a deep understanding, without any logical reasoning, based on his knowledge and skills, experiences, pedagogical skills and intelligence, based on his intuition, he should make a quick and clear decision, correct his attitude and personal pedagogical activity depending on the change of the situation, and organically apply this decision in the process of rhetoric with students. A young teacher, who has just started his professional career, must regularly analyze himself and have in-depth knowledge of:

- to have in-depth knowledge of his educational subject and to know the studied material thoroughly and perfectly;

- Pedagogical - psychological and methodical preparation for rhetorical relationship with students;

- to have studied the internal psychological characteristics of each student and team;

- be able to behave freely and control his mental and psychological feelings;

- acquisition of professional skills of rhetorical communication with the audience;

- ability to demonstrate high examples of pedagogical culture, development of pedagogical thinking and worldview;

- be able to create a technological map of training based on the criteria for choosing tools and methods suitable for the purpose, task and content of teaching subjects;

- to anticipate possible pedagogical situations and to take drastic measures against them.

The success of pedagogical training in rhetorical communication with students largely depends on the teacher's continuous acquisition of communicative skills and competences, and the ability to use them.

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